

Acknowledgement

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Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Thallium(I) and Indium(III) N-Glycylglycine Complexes

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ON account of the increased significance of the sulphur containing organic compounds¹⁻⁵ and amino acids in pharmaceutical and industrial field, considerable interest regarding their electrochemical behaviour has been shown in the past two decades.

This communication reports the polarographic determination of the composition and stability constants of Tl(I) and In(III) complexes with N-glycylglycine at 30° and 40°.

Experimental

N-glycylglycine (NH₂CH₂CONH CH₂COOH) was supplied by B.D.H. Chemicals Ltd. Poole, England and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR B.D.H. grade.

In case of Tl(I) N-glycylglycine complexes, the concentration of metal ion was 1.0 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton-X-100 at pH=3.8 (maintained by HClO₄ and NaOH). The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.04 to 0.12M.

In case of In(III) N-glycylglycine complexes, the concentration of metal ion was 0.5 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton-X-100.

The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.04 to 0.12M.

Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the current-voltage curves. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 0.1M supporting electrolyte (NaClO₄); m=2.953 mg/sec., t=2.5 sec/drop at h=43.5 cm and -0.4 V vs S.C.E.

Results and Discussion

The current-voltage curves of Tl(I) and In(III) in presence of different concentrations of N-glycylglycine are plotted at 30° and 40°. In each case a single well defined cathodic wave appeared. All the plots of log (i/i_d-i) vs -E_{d,e.} yielded straight lines and the slopes agreed with the reversibility of the reduction. The cathodic shift in E_{1/2} coupled with decrease in diffusion current on increasing N-glycylglycine concentration shows the complex formation with Tl(I) and In(III) ions, respectively. The plot of i_d vs h_{eff}^{1/2} was found to be linear, indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction of Tl(I) and In(III) complexes.

The curvature obtained in the plot of -E_{1/2} vs -log C_x showed the successive complex formation and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{6,7} was adopted for deriving various functions F₁(X). From the experimental data, the complexity function F₁(X) which is polynomial in (X), is set up; the coefficients of the latter are required, β_n. The graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation to N-equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below:

Tl(I)N-glycylglycine complexes

$$\beta_1 = 6, \quad \beta_2 = 11, \quad \beta_3 = 920 \text{ at } 30^\circ \\ \text{and } \beta_1 = 4, \quad \beta_2 = 5, \quad \beta_3 = 740 \text{ at } 40^\circ$$

In(III) N-glycylglycine complexes

$$\beta_1 = 2, \quad \beta_2 = 100, \quad \beta_3 = 9400 \text{ at } 30^\circ \\ \text{and } \beta_1 = 4, \quad \beta_2 = 120, \quad \beta_3 = 8800 \text{ at } 40^\circ$$

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Mercury(II) Complexes with Substituted Aminobenzothiazoles

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CAMPBELL and his coworkers have reported¹ cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with 2-amino-benzothiazole. Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with substituted amino thiazoles have also been studied^{2,3} in detail. The present communication describes the reactions of 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole towards mercury(II) ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The substituted aminobenzothiazoles have been prepared by standard procedure.

A mixture of methanol solutions of the mercury salt and the substituted aminobenzothiazole (1 : 2 ratio) was refluxed (15 minutes to 1 hour) and cooled when crystalline compounds separated out. These were filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Mercury content in the complexes was estimated complexometrically by EDTA method and nitrogen

and sulfur by standard procedure. Conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Unicam SP-1025 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the ten complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type $[HgL_2X_2]$, where $L=2$ -amino-6-methylbenzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole, and $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , OAc^- . The complexes are white to greyish white in colour, have low melting points and are soluble in acetone, the solution being non-electrolytes (Λ_M being in the range of 20-30 mhos. cm^2).

The appearance of a sharp peak in the IR spectra around 815 cm^{-1} in the free ligands can be assigned to $\nu(C-S)$ vibration. On complexation with Hg(II) ion, this frequency has been shifted down to lower frequency region $\sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating possible bonding of benzothiazole to the metal ion through the ring sulfur atom. The bands observed $\sim 1535\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 3250 cm^{-1} in free ligand are due to $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations respectively. No remarkable shift of these two bands has been noticed in the complexes, which proves that both the endo and exocyclic nitrogen atoms are not coordinated to the metal ion. The positions of $\nu(C-N)$, $\nu(C-S)$ and δNCS bands in the thiocyanate complex are indicative of S-bonded thiocyanate⁴⁻⁷. The carboxylates give⁸ a strong asymmetric stretching band near $1650-1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a weaker symmetrical stretching band near 1400 cm^{-1} . In the present investigation two sharp peaks appeared at 1650 cm^{-1} and 1395 cm^{-1} , which can be assignable to $\nu\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \text{as} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{array}\right)$ and $\nu\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \text{s} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{array}\right)$ vibrations.

In the nitrate complex ν_4 and ν_1 bands (NO_3 asymmetric and symmetric stretch) appear at 1450 cm^{-1} and 1280 cm^{-1} respectively. The position of ν_4 and ν_1 and their separation $\Delta\nu$ of 130 cm^{-1} suggests^{9,10}, the nitrate group to be monodentate.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, IR AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Λ_M mhos cm^2	%Hg		%Nitrogen		%Sulfur		(C-S)	%Inhibition	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		<i>P. oryzae</i> 400 ppm	<i>H. oryzae</i> 1000 ppm
1.	HgL ₂ Cl ₂	26.5	30.97	31.32	8.59	8.74	9.74	9.99	800	—	—
2.	HgL ₂ Br ₂	20.4	27.21	27.50	7.46	7.67	8.41	8.77	808	—	—
3.	HgL ₂ I ₂	10.8	24.08	24.36	6.67	6.80	7.58	7.77	805	—	—
4.	HgL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	20.2	28.53	28.93	11.95	12.11	9.08	9.22	798	—	—
5.	HgL ₂ (OAc) ₂	10.4	28.86	29.17	9.37	9.53	10.72	10.89	800	—	—
6.	HgL' ₂ Cl ₂	12.8	33.08	33.46	9.18	9.36	10.46	10.67	800	—	—
7.	HgL' ₂ Br ₂	17.6	28.71	29.14	8.02	8.13	9.08	9.29	805	74.8/51.5	69.1/62.8
8.	HgL' ₂ I ₂	12.9	25.29	25.63	7.05	7.15	8.03	8.17	800	—	—
9.	HgL' ₂ (SCN) ₂	13.1	30.87	31.12	12.92	13.03	19.68	19.85	795	64.9/21.8	59.3/18.6
10.	HgL' ₂ (OAc) ₂	10.7	30.75	31.02	8.53	8.66	9.72	9.89	805	60.0/18.3	66.1/32.2

L=2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole, L'=2-Amino-6-methyl benzothiazole.

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